

RESOLUTION OF MICROPITTING FOR CASE CARBURISED HELICAL GEAR PAIR VIA TOOTH PROFILE MODIFICATION

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Abstract

Helical gears play a vital role in terms of power transmission in parallel shaft gears. They are subjected to various conditions of load, speed, temperature, and ambient conditions. These gears are normally case carburised for higher torque transmission. High torque transmission capability also brings surface related fatigue stress which results in surface related failure. Micropitting is one such surface related failure which starts on tooth flank in terms of surface texture change. This may further grow in magnitude and result in catastrophic failure. This research work is performed to compare the results of analytical and experimental investigation for the possible micropitting initiative zone. Analytical approach is carried out by using the KISSsys model and the experimental work is carried out by using a dynamometer test rig to apply the load on the gearbox shaft for a defined load cycle. To ensure the change in the gear surface gear profile analysis is done with the help of Zeiss CMM machine having gearpro program. It was clearly visible that the micropitting has initiated below the pitch line of pinion. Tooth profile is later modified with lead and crown modification. With this modification it was found that the effect of micropitting has been disappeared for the same testing cycle time. This result was also verified in terms of gear profile view.

Keywords: Micropitting, GearPro, Kisssys, Dynamometer

Nomenclature

Symbol	Description	Units
b	Face width	mm
f_i'	Single flank tooth to tooth composite error	μm
F_i'	Single flank total composite error testing	μm
F_i''	Double flank total composite error testing	μm
f_i''	Tangential load	N
F_p	Total cumulative pitch error	μm
F_β	Total alignment error	μm
F_r	Radial Runout	μm
F_f	Total profile error	μm
f_{pe}	Load Distribution Factor	μm
$f_{H\beta}$	Flank line angle error	μm
f_p	Individual pitch error	μm
TRA	Helix evaluation length	μm
ω_1	Pinion rpm	rpm
ω_2	Gear rpm	rpm
ρ_1	Radius of curvature pinion	mm
ρ_2	Radius of curvature gear	mm

INTRODUCTION

There has been much evidence showing the micropitting as one of the critical yet least known reason for gear failures. It is found in abundance in case hardened gears. Helical gears on account of helical contact and overlap ratio provide smooth meshing but is accompanied by frictional losses also. These losses become more evident in the case of low-speed pair.

This research work is about the effect of tooth profile modification on micropitting. Both analytical and experimental analysis is performed to ensure the comparison and effect of modification on micropitting.

1.1 Specific Sliding

Gear pair while operating roll and slide over each other. Fig-1 shows the rolling and sliding parameter of pinion and gear with subscript 1 and 2 respectively. Over rolling and sliding action rolling action is always preferred because it allows the entrance of lubricant between the meshing teeth which results in corresponding increase in oil film thickness. On the contrary sliding velocity is detrimental as it releases heat, lowers the gear pair performance, and increased the asperity distress. It also shears the oil film thickness thus reducing the effective lubricant film thickness in the contact area under sliding. As shown in the Figure-1 the rolling velocity magnitude increases from zero at interference point to max at the end of contact point shown as SAP and EAP for both gear and pinion the distance between the rolling velocity vector of Pinion and Gear represents the sliding velocity as shown in the Figure-1. The relative sliding velocity at any point of contact on contact line is given as a product of distance of the concerned point from pitch point to the sum of angular velocities of Pinion and gear.

Figure 1: Rolling and sliding Velocity

$$V_{r1} = \omega_1 * \rho_1 \tag{1}$$

$$V_{r2} = \omega_2 * \rho_2 \tag{2}$$

$$V_{s1} = V_{r1} - V_{r2} \tag{3}$$

$$V_{s2} = -V_{s1} \tag{4}$$

$$V_e = V_{r1} + V_{r2} \tag{5}$$

Similarly specific sliding ratio can be given as below:

$$V_{ss1} = \frac{V_{s1}}{V_{r1}} \tag{6}$$

$$V_{ss2} = \frac{V_{s2}}{V_{r2}} \tag{7}$$

Equation 6 and 7 provides the way to calculate the specific sliding ratio which is dimensionless parameter such that it is positive in addenda with a range from zero to +1. Its value is zero at pitch point whereas +1 is at the interference point with mating gear. Its value is negative for dedenda with zero value at pitch point and $-\infty$ at interference point. Negative sliding refers to opposite direction for sliding to rolling direction. Negative sliding is important as it promotes Hertzian Fatigue.

1.2 Gear Accuracies

Generally, for the functional requirement, gear errors need to be controlled and is classified into four functional groups as shown in Table-1.

Table-1: Function Group of Deviation

Functional Group		Important Deviations
G	Uniformity of the transmission of movement	$F'_i, f'_i, F''_i, f''_i, F_r, F_p$
L	Smooth running and dynamic loading capacity	$f'_i, f_{H\beta}, f''_i, F_r, F_p, F_f, f_p, f_{pe}$
T	Static load Capacity	$f_{H\beta}, f_{pe}, TRA$
N	No indication of the function	$F''_i, f_{H\beta}, F_f, f''_i$

A single gear tooth quality, such as quality 6, is suggested whenever a specific gear requires general maintenance property without taking individual operational requirements into account. For other case the fulfilment is done by adding the specific functional group with gear quality like L6. L6 means gear with quality grade 6 and it need to be taken care for smooth running and dynamic loading capacity. To streamline the testing requirement these are further subcategorised in A, B and C. In our case it is B.

1.3 Present concern

The rigorous usage of gearbox for mixing application deals with continuous loaded duty for almost 12 hours per day basis. Such gears are subjected with surface related failure more as compared to root related fatigue bending failure. Based on the field experience, micropitting is observed on the

tooth flank below the pitch circle but this behaviour is not common for all gears used in mixing industry. Gear pair considered in this research work are subjected to micropitting in the predicted zone and there needs a means to avoid it.

To continue the research, work the most popular gear pair is considered as per Table-1

Table 2: Gear Pair Data

Parameter	Pinion	Gear
No of teeth	24	97
Normal Module	1	
Helix Angle (degree)	13-24'-8"	
Pressure Angle (degree)	20	
Rpm	160	39.6
Material-Case hardened and Ground	20MnCr5	

Gear and Pinion is Case hardened and ground. The quality grade is considered as Grade -6 as per ISO:1328. Gear pair need to analysed for various parameters based on past work done to find a way to avoid or reduce the micropitting.

1.4 Literature Review

To understand Micropitting various set of experimentation and related research has been carried since long till now. During investigation of past research work through Literature review it was found that the experimentations were considered on various testing setup starting from roller disc to actual gears in controlled environment.

H.Liu et al. [1], analyzed the various research work done to take care of micro pitting of steel gears from past data. Tooth contact pattern was analyzed between modified and unmodified gears to observe the stress pattern and their values. Various tooth surface with different roughness values were analyzed to observe the contact fatigue failure risk. One of the interesting analysis was to find the effect of surface wear on micropitting. Wear depth of gear and pinions were plotted along the line of action. As this was the review research work, it also involved the lubricant effect and various gear testing equipment like FZG, PCS instrument. It was concluded that micropitting can be reduced by microscopic and macroscopic geometry modification. It was also observed that micropitting initiated on account of contact pressure whereas its propagation is driven by specific sliding. Addition of the wear process to it was further deteriorating the condition and micropitting was more visible.

M. N. Webster et al. [2], concentrated on the factors influencing the micropitting enhancement. Various operating parameters were reviewed. To perform the experiment roller disc machine setup was used. Different geometrical modification like flat and chamfered profile were used with material 17CrMo6 having hardness 58HRC and 60HRC respectively. Both items were grounded on OD. Roller disc machine as expected has shown the micropitting in the dedendum zone. It was observed that the microprinting occurred on surfaces having relatively low speed. Increasing the

surface finish caused the increase in specific film thickness and was the useful method to avoid the micropitting. Slide to roll ratio was also reviewed that reducing its magnitude retards micropitting as well. Overall, it was the slide to roll ratio, surface finish and load were the potential reason for micropitting and taking necessary action to them could help in reducing the micropitting.

Dario Croccolo et al. [3] presented a work to meet the current competitive environment of better efficiency, torque transmission this research work is an important reference. It has been a detailed work of data collection from practical examples to define the process and relevant parameters for gear design. Spur gear pair was the subject of this research work. Two different materials are considered to investigate the hardening effect as 18NiCrMo5 & 41CrAlMo7. Tooth pairs were with Asymmetric and symmetric construction. Methodology of gear design started from initial steps from start of module selection to system design. Apart from gear design the lubrication system and its application was the important area of research work. This also detailed the way of preparing the drawings and technical parameters required to manufacture a gear.

Hasan Ozturk et al. [4] include topics related to the gear defects along with contact ratio with its effect and way to measurement of effect. Time and Frequency domain and related research are the priority of this research work. As the work was related to detection of pitting Test rig used was with pitted gears in a two-stage helical gearbox, Input and output of the gearbox was equipped with Induction motor and DC motor. Induction motor was being as a source of power input whereas the DC motor was acting as a source of load bank. DC motor which was acting as a load bank, because of its power capacity the face width of the gear pair were reduced to 4mm from 12mm width. Accelerometer in perpendicular position was used to each other to capture the vibration signals. To examine the response of healthy gears with pitted gears various curves were drawn. Frequency signals were considered as a mean to know the pitting in gears. Amplitude of vibration was considered as indicative of the pitting growth.

A Oila et al.[5], investigative work of this research work was aligned for the micro pitted gears. Idea was to know how the martensitic layer alters during the micro pitting process. Case carburized in gaseous medium helical gears were considered. Back-to-Back test rig was the experimental test rig. Loading were considered from 5 million cycles to 50 million cycles. Lubricating oil was used was Mineral oil. Scanning electron microscope was used to determine the surface condition after testing.

B R Hohn et al.[6] displayed a piece of work on the Influence of oil temperature on gear failures. Oil's viscosity gets reduced as its temperature rises, this reduces the thickness of oil which results in the creation of thin film between the meshing gear flanks. Elevated temperatures sometimes cause detrimental effect in lubricating oil, allowing their chemical elements to react with adjacent materials which sometimes affect the endurance limit of the gears also. Lubricating oils must be selected based on the temperature condition and the environment for which it is subjected to. Thermal calculation and contact analysis is required to know the temperature rise and so that the lubricating oil can be selected accordingly.

L. Winkelmann et al. [7], experimental kit used was Standard FZG gear test setup. Baseline and superfinished gears were used in this experimental testing. Baseline gears which were unmodified version of specification of FVA information sheet 54 and superfinished gears were also as per FVA information sheet but were finished using chemically accelerated vibratory finishing method. Case Carburized gears were considered with material of 16MnCr5 and having quality grade 5. Load stage test and Endurance test were considered for both pair of gears with defined load cycles. Visual effects of micropitting were considered as one of the result analyses whereas the profile deviation was the other parameter which was considered as checking points. Profile deviation value was observed more in base line gears than the superfinished gears.

M.A. Muraro et al. [8] exhibited on the influence of contact stress distribution and specific film thickness on the wear of Spur gears During Pitting tests. FZG test setup was used as testing setup for this research work. AISI 8620 steel was used as Gear material. It was manufactured by shaving and milling operation. Two Torque values of 135Nm and steady state Torque value of 302 Nm with corresponding test temperatures of 60 degree and 90 degrees Celsius respectively were considered for Whole experiment. Gear image was analyzed to find the wear levels on the gear surfaces. Load sharing functions has huge influence on gear surface deterioration. Resistance to Wear was found inversely proportional with high surface finish value.

I.S. Al-Tubi et al. [9], presented his work on an experimental and analytical examination of gear micropitting initiation and propagation under fluctuated loading circumstances is presented.. Analytical and experimental approach is used here to continue and compare the investigation. Strong initiative was there to find the relation between varying load and micropitting initiation. ISO TC 15144-1 was used to investigate the analytical approach. Initial pit formation was analyzed while initial load cycles along with its propagation. This finding was compared with the analytical approach. Pinion addendum zone was the point where micropitting initiated initially. Pitting was getting engraved towards addendum over a period of time. Analytical approach identified lubricant film thickness and contact stress values as the responsible term for micropitting. Along with these other parameters were identified as surface finish of gears.

Michael Hein et al. [10] elaborate his work on the Parametric study on the calculated risk of tooth flank fracture of case-hardened gears. This investigation gives an important insight for crack propagation below tooth surface. Analytical approach was carried through the ISO standard technical report after considering various parameters as guided by the standard document. Due to recent development and high surface finish condition, it was found that it is quite possible to control the micropitting but it may lead to other type of failure like sub surface crack initiation. To find the correlation of analytical work experimentation was done on FZG test setup. Numerous parameters were considered for the experimental analysis which included both external factor like load cycle, lubricant to internal geometric factor like tooth profile etc. ISO technical document was very much in line with FZG test, and the results were also satisfactory.

Aleks Vrcek et al. [11], emphasized on micropitting and wear characterization for different rolling bearing steels. This research work is useful for the work related to different surface hardness and

methodologies followed on the surfaces. Bearing steels are under consideration for this research work. Discs are formed in the form these materials are subjected to high contact stress with lower lubricant film thickness. Hardening of these discs were done by different hardness process. Asperities plasticity was evaluated using Tribo testing. Surface failure was an important function of surface hardness variation among discs. Plain medium carbon steel behaved better than alloy steel from surface fatigue point of view. Surface roughness was the other parameter which was observed that a harder surface with poor surface finish was getting deteriorated earlier than comparatively softer surface with lower hardness.

Robin Olson et al. [12], presented a case study of ISO/TS 6336-22 Micropitting calculation. High speed gear set test was first initiated with centrifugal compressor. Micropitting was observed in Pinion dedendum which later travelled to the addendum. Same gear set was tested through ISO standard analytically and the charts were plotted against the lubricant film thickness and stress on the gear tooth surface. The results were in comparison with the experimental work. The second work was done for the investigation of wind turbine gear test setup. Similar set work was performed with analytical and experimental approach and the results were compared to each other. In this part also the graphs were plotted with specific film thickness at two temperatures of 50 degree and 70 degree Celsius. All three cases were considered with helical gears. Geometries of the gears were arranged in such a way that different slide to roll ratio can be availed. For all the there cases, different Torque ratings were considered as 265Nm, 300Nm and 400Nm respectively. Lubricant oil M-200EP was considered for each case and specific film thickness was determines too.

Nadine Sagraloff et al.[13], worked on profile modification and its effects are analyzed experimentally. Test gears were developed for the micropitting test. 16MnCr5 and 18CrNiMo7-6 were considered for the test gears with micro geometry, macro geometry and profile grinding method. For experimental part FZG back-to-back setup was used for this experiment. Test rig included both test gears and slave gears. Both gears were arranged as per standard practice. Test gear and slave gears were case hardened. New approach usage and the methods followed were almost similar.

Mao Ueda et al.[14], founded the effect of friction on micropitting. Ball on disc test rig was considered. This test rig was having an arrangement to trace the lubricant film thickness while experimentation. Friction was varied by using oil with different content. Other different variant of lubricating oils were explored for this experiment to analyze the results. Graphs were prepared between Friction parameter with respect to the load cycles during experimentation. 8 million cycles were considered as target load cycle. Ball's surface got damaged due to friction and it was visible under 200-micron vision. Defects were found as the function of the load cycles which were directly proportional to each other. Side by side surface finish of disc was also getting affected. Various graphs of different oil film thickness was clearly showing that lower the oil film thickness and more was the surface defects.

• **Outcome of Literature survey**

Literature reviews were related to wide range of problems with different variant of problem ranging from disc to gears. The study of these research paper has provided the direction to way ahead for the current experimental work. The finding is detailed as below:

- All the forces, sliding and rolling is occurring online of contact and is an important parameter for analytical as well as experimental work.
- Lubricants must be selected according to the operating temperature it is subjected to along with environmental condition.
- Gear surface failure is more affected by varying load acting on it even for the same gear speed.
- Contact line includes the complete meshing cycle load and shall be analyzed carefully.
- Gearbox must be designed as per international standard to maintain uniformity and rule out unseen load effects.
- Lubricant film thickness below 1 micrometer has good correspondence standard material whereas for more than 1 micrometer micropitting may occur and there is no suitable guideline for it.
- Specific sliding produces friction and has detrimental effect on gear surface and must be reduced as small as possible.
- Surface finish of the gear pair has inverse proportional relation with miropitting growth.
- Very fewer research is available with material 20MnCr5 as compared to 18CrNiMo-7-6 or 16MnCr material.
- Not any of the research work was found for gears in mixing applications.
- Actual research works with helical gears for similar scope as of this research work were not available.
- Gear profile modification can be useful in gear surface related failure issues.

1.5 Research parameter for experimental work.

From the last section of literature review it was clear that Loads, surface finish, Lubricant, surface hardness, friction on account of sliding speed are the main parameter responsible for micropitting. In the current research work load and specific sliding are considered as the main parameter whereas other parameters like lubricant, surface finish, surface hardness are considered as non-affecting parameters because they are considered in the best possible form and achievable from cost and engineering process point of view. Out of these parameters lubricant parameter is considered constant and hence the lubricant is selected suitably. Surface hardness and surface finish are material property and is almost frozen once 20MnCr5 material is selected with manufacturing

quality grade 5. Lubricant is also selected based on the maximum usage and availability in the current market scenario.

1.6 Gear tooth modification to reduce the sliding speed.

Gear pair while meshing with each other possess rolling as well as sliding velocity. Rolling velocity is desirable while sliding velocity is not. However, it is not possible to eliminate the sliding velocity. We can control the sliding velocity to minimum value and balance it on both gear and pinion end. Exhaustive analysis is performed in KISSOFT to get the desired profile shift value to have balanced specific sliding ratio.

Figure 2: Balance Specific sliding

Figure-2 shows the graph showing the specific sliding values for the gear pair. Gear 1 refers to the pinion and Gear 2 refers to the Gear. In the Figure 2, upper allowance s are shown with minimum value as -1.041629 and maximum value as 0.502704 for Pinion whereas the same values for gear are -1.010876 and 0.510195 respectively. Lower allowance value for both Pinion and gear are very close to the upper allowance as -0.929121 minimum and 0.497717 maximum for Pinion whereas -0.990910 minimum and 0.481629 maximum for Gear. The value with limits looks very closer for both Pinion and Gear and can be considered for balance specific sliding condition. This value is achieved by statistical analysis following for various profile shifts, profile modification, and crowning effect applied to gear and pinion both.

1.7 Software used in this Research.

Kissys 2020 is used, for gear and shaft calculation, Finsap is used for the gear casing analysis.

1.8 Gear Pair Analysis

Gear and Pinion are re calculated as existing in the KISSYS 2020 without any change in any parameter to understand the its behaviour for various parameters. After doing this analysis gear

pair are subjected to geometric modification based on the detail's statistical analysis so that the detrimental effect of actual gear pair can be reduced.

- Specific sliding of gear and Pinion

Figure 3: Specific sliding of Gear and Pinion Premodification

Figure 4: Specific sliding of Gear and Pinion Post modification

Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows the specific sliding of gear and Pinion before and after modification of gear tooth. Because of Balance specific sliding and tooth modification the same gear pair is having the difference in their sliding value zone. Post modification the sliding speed value has improved for both Pinion and Gear.

• Gear Pair Mesh

Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the mesh pattern of gear pair pre modification and post modification.

Figure 5: Mesh Pattern Pre modification

Figure 6: Mesh Pattern Post modification

There is marginal or no difference in between the speed and Torque carrying perspective of the gear pair in pre and post modification status. The green dotted line shows the line of contact and there is a difference on account of tooth modification in Figure 6 whereas the contact ratio is still above 1.4

• **Transmission error**

Figure 7 and Figure 8 shows the effect of transmission error of the gear pair pre and post modification..

Figure 7: Transmission Error Pre modification

Figure 8: Transmission Error Post modification

There is a slight improvement in the transmission error over the rotation of pinion is observed. Transmission error looks to be shifted towards the pitch point and trying to maintain the equilibrium rather than being concentrated in one zone. However, it is not completely resolved.

Post modification there is slight uprise in magnitude at the end and start of contact of pinion, but it is marginal and has no counter effect. Acceleration graph shows clear shift of error in the addendum zone as compared to dedendum zone of pinion. The maximum magnitude of acceleration is however showing same as peak point in both pre and post modification.

• **Single Contact Stiffness value**

Figure 9 and Figure 10 shows the difference in the single contact stiffness value of gear pair pre and post modification.

Figure 9: Single contact stiffness value pre modification

Figure 10: Single contact stiffness value post modification

From the above shown Figures specific pair stiffness has improved in post modification stage as compared to pre modification stage. Tilting stiffness value has gone down as the maximum load is applicable at the centre of tooth in modified version as compared to unmodified version. Other parameters are also showing substantial improvement.

- **Torque and Speed curve**

Figure 11 and Figure 12 shows the Torque and speed curve of the gear pair in pre modified condition and post modified condition..

Figure 11: Torque and Speed curve Pre modification

Figure 12: Torque and Speed Curve Post modification

Torque Curve in Pre modified pinion is much steeper than what it is shown in post modified condition. Sudden decrease in or increase in speed brings sliding speed also in picture. This nature of speed change cannot be eliminated however can be improved as it is totally dependent on the geometry of revolution and varying radius of curvature throughout the flank. This behaviour can be easily viewed in the Speed curve where the curve is not smooth line but a curvy line with many peaks which shoes huge variation of speed over the angle of rotation. Both Torque and speed curve has improved in the dedendum zone. The addendum zone is more or less similar in both pre and post modified condition. Both Torque and speed peaks have increased in the post modified condition of gear pair.

- **Contact Temperature**

Figure 13 and Figure 14 shows the contact temperature distribution in gears while meshing.

Figure 13: Contact Temperature Pre modification

Figure 14: Contact Temperature Post modification

From Figure 13 and Figure 14 it is clear that the maximum temperature value has remained same. The occurrence of the contact temperature has changed with respect to the rotation angle. Because of the tooth modification the start and end of the contact has reduced. Same parameter is also depicted on the pinion tooth view where the temperature pattern is shown on flank line. This is moving the start of point of contact away from the tip of mating gear where there was very high friction.

• **Specific Film Thickness**

Figure 15 shows the specific lubricant film thickness variation over the entire contact line. It is the property of lube film thickness and surface finish of material. The pattern of this property is same for both pre and post modification.

Figure 15: Specific Film Thickness Pre and Post modification

• **Profile Diagram**

Figure 16 shows the profile diagram with both modified and unmodified status of Pinion.

Figure 16: Pinion Profile diagram Pre and Post modification

Pre and post modification of profile diagram clearly shows the difference between the teeth profile and the modification offered in the post modification status. The manufactured and used profile shall be in between the blue and red curve.

- **Contact line and Contact pattern**

Figure 17 and Figure 18 shows the contact line difference in Pre and post modification version.

Figure 17: Pinion Contact line diagram Pre modification

As per Figure 17 the loading pattern is starting from Side II and ending to Side I of the face width. The ends of face width are deflecting because of the cantilever load. Any lateral deflection in the tooth is deteriorating the contact pattern of gear set. This will damage the gear surface. To take care of this tooth surface is modified with crowning so that the load gets concentrated at centre as shown in post modification.

Figure 18: Pinion contact line diagram Post modification

Crowning of teeth at centre provides the increase in the stiffness at centre of the teeth also. Parallely since the teeth profile is curved so the contact area is also reduced causing the high load concentration at centre of face width as shown in the Figure -18. Because of low contact area

which is taking the complete load the magnitude of load has also increased as compared to pre modified version. But this is not affecting the tooth deflection as at centre of tooth the stiffness is very high which can easily take care of this load. Thus, the tooth contact pattern remains unaffected even after high load as shown in post modified version.

Contact line is also showing the same pattern which contact pattern is shown. Contact line is the line of contact about which all the forces are getting transmitted and contact pattern represents the contact over wide face width along the contact line.

• **Tooth Trace diagram**

Tooth trace diagram shows the tooth modification along the face width. Figure 19 and Figure 20 clearly shows the tooth modification of pre and post modification.

Figure 19: Contact Pattern pre modification

The above figure shows that there is no modification in the tooth form and the blue line along with red line shows the boundary limit. The grey line shows the tolerance range. This is purely defined as per the accuracy grade of the gears as defined. Manufacturing must be in between the red and blue line within tolerance zone.

Figure 20: Contact Pattern post modification

The above figure shows that there is modification in the tooth form and the blue line along with red line shows the boundary limit. This is usually done for the mating flank but here it is done for both the flank. Also known as crowning effect help in increasing the stiffness of gear at mid of face width.

• **Hertzian Pressure Distribution pattern**

Figure 21 shows the Hertzian stress distribution pre and post modification on the gear pair contact line.

Figure 21: Hertzian stress distribution pre and post modification

As shown in the above figure the stress distribution over the contact line has changed to smooth curve from sharp peaks as shown in pre modified version. This help in gradual stress distribution over the contact zone helps in avoiding high stress concentration zone.

1.9 Experimental setup

Figure 22: Testing Setup

Experimental setup consists of a powder dynamometer as a source of applying the required torque at the gearbox output shaft. Powder Dynamometer was equipped with torque meter to measure and ensure the torque to which the gearbox is subjected to. Gearbox was connected to the dynamometer through its low-speed shaft connected via torque meter. Gearbox input shaft relates to the input power source to provide the rpm and input torque as per need. Vibration sensor, oil sensor, current sensors were mounted to gearbox and power source to measure and ensure the control environment condition.

1.10 Load cycle consideration

Micropitting is Fatigue related phenomena. It is necessary to take care of the loading parameters such that in a short period of testing time similar loading environment can be created as applicable to Fatigue load testing. Gear pair is designed at .5 Hp for 20000hours. A reverse calculation is done with varying load cycle to ensure that the gear is subjected to similar environment to which it is subjected during its actual working life.

Since the application to which this gearbox is used have constant speed so speed of input and output shall remain same throughout the testing period. Power source to this gearbox is of 1 HP and is very much eligible to deliver high torque as per the consumed torque. The Torque value can be varied at the output shaft with the help of Powder dynamometer and the same can be recorded as well. To ensure the control environment the temperature parameter of oils is also monitored throughout the testing cycle.

Table 2: Load Cycle data

Step	Time(hours)	Power (Kw)	Input Rpm	Output rpm	Torque (Nm) @ Input	Torque (Nm) @ Output	Load cycle-Pinion	Load cycle-Gear
1	51	0.75	160	40	45	180	489600	122400
2	336	0.5	160	40	30	120	3225600	806400

Based on the detailed calculation above data was showing the similar effect on gear pair which in actual the gear pair would be subjected in its whole actual life. Reason for two rating was to ensure the high-power requirement while mixing different density and viscosity fluid in actual working life.

1.11 Actual Manufacturing of components

- Gear housing

Gear housing is manufactured with Aluminium, AL-6061 T6 material. The T6 refers to the temper or degree of hardness, which is achieved by precipitation hardening. Machining process is carried over the vertical machining centre machine BFW BMV 50 TC24. Images while manufacturing is shown below in Figure 15:

Figure 23: Gear casing

• **Gear Pair manufacturing and assembly**

Gear and Pinion was manufactured with 20MnCr5 material. Conventional hobbing machine is used to cut the gear and later the grinding machine was used to provide the ground surface as per need after case hardening. Images while manufacturing is shown below in Figure 16. Bearings used in the assembly was 6006-2z and 61904-2z which are life long lubricated bearings and don't need external lubricants to work.

Figure 24: Gear pair manufacturing and assembly

1.12 Results and Finding

a. **Vibration reading and finding.**

Figure 25: Accelerometer reading pre and Post modification.

Accelerometer reading is plotted above for the worst values recorded over a period of testing. As against the limit value a sufficient margin was observed between the limit and actual value. It was observed that the assembly couldn't get damaged to pass the limit of vibration. Some peaks were observed which was because of external effects. The nature of curve for both pre and post modification was found similar.

b. Gear flank Surface Visualization

Figure 26: Gear Surface snap pre and post modification

Experimentation was run for two sets one with gears without modification and other with modifications. After the testing the gears were cleaned, and their snaps were taken. The highlighted zone in the Figure shows the signs of micro pitting. The figure shown on the right-hand side shows no such changes on the flank surface for the same duty cycles. The micropitting was observed in Pinion only and that also in dedendum zone.

c. Pinion Profile variation.

Figure 27: Profile diagram of Pinion pre and post modification after experimentation

Gear profile measurement was done post experimentation for both the pinion which get micropitted and one which was not having any sign of micropitting. As shown in the picture the profile diagram of mating flank was totally damaged as compared to non-mating flank of same gear. On the contrary the modified pinion was still able to maintain the good tooth profile as required. This shows that the profile was getting deteriorated if not properly defined and modified and finally causing the micropitting.

d. Microstructure comparison

Figure 28: Microstructure comparison of micropitted pinion and new pinion.

Spare piece of unmodified pinion and micropitted piece was sent to lab for microstructural analysis. The magnification used here was 1000x. From the available Figure no clear distinction was observed and hence it became difficult to identify if microstructure changes on account of micropitting.

e. Oil and Temperature Data

Oil and temperature data of lubricating oil was captured for 320 times the data were plotted as below in Figure 29. TDN no kept on decreasing over a period whereas there was change in temperature also. The pattern remained same for both the experiments. TDN no kept on decreasing over days and maintained the constant value of 900 which can be considered as good value yet on lower side. Similarly, the oil temperature also increased to the maximum limit of 80 degree Celsius as against the allowable limit of oil temperature as 120 degree Celsius.

Figure 29: Oil temperature and TDN no details

f. FEA approach

Micropitted surface was analyzed for surface deterioration and the same was modeled in KISSYS for surface deterioration to find out the effect on its performance. Data from the actual deviation s in profile were fed to the software to generate the tooth surface. Following points were further observed.

• Meshing pattern

After modeling the pinion and gear the meshing pattern was investigated. The meshing pattern is shown as below in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Mesh Pattern Deteriorated pair.

Because of the deterioration of the tooth profile the meshing pattern was found completely deteriorated. Green dotted line shows the line of contact which also look like to be completely disturbed. Speed values looks to be less distorted as compared to Torque cycle. Availability of local stress point on gear flank also validate this point.

• Transmission Error

Figure 31 and Figure 32 shows a comparison of Transmission error with the modified gear having no defects with the defective gear.

Figure 31: Transmission error as expected vs actual after surface deterioration

Figure 32: Transmission error acceleration as expected vs actual after surface deterioration

Left Figure in the above Figure-31 and Figure 32, shows the condition with a good condition new pinion. The transmission error curve looks to be smooth and follow a mirror pattern like. For the transmission error acceleration curve there are some spikes and mostly coming due to manufacturing deviations. Same values are shown on right figure of Figure 31 and Figure 32 and they are with big differences as compared to the un defected pinion. The transmission error range has increased for the micropitted gear model as compared to new manufactured pinion model. The values of Transmission error acceleration shows a huge spike in the values and the same effect can be seen on gear surface with some marks after completing the testing.

● Lubricant film thickness comparison

Lubricant film thickness was calculated for both actual manufactured gear model and micropitted gear model. Figure 33 shows the lubricant film thickness for actual manufactured gear model(left side) and micropitted gear model(right side).

Figure 33: Lube Film Thickness for undefected gear and micropitted gear model

The minimum possible lube film thickness for the manufactured gear without any micropitting on surface was 0.015 micrometer as compared to the micropitted gear model where the thickness of oil film near the pitch line has become almost negligible and thus raising the concerned point for micropitting. Because of deteriorated tooth profile the micropitting model is showing no oil film thickness near the pitch line in dedendum area. This is purely defined based on the tooth deviation values observed from the measurement of micropitted gear. Marks of micropitting was visible near the pitch line in dedendum zone after actual experimentation for pinion.

● Contact Pattern change

Figure 34 shows the comparison of contact pattern of a healthy pinion used in this experiment with the surface deteriorated pinion.

Figure 34: Contact pattern for new modified pinion(left) and wear pinion model (right)

Contact pattern shown on the left-hand side is for new modified pinion which even after the complete experimentation still maintain the same contact pattern where the pinion model on right hand side shows the contact pattern has completely deteriorated. Based on the transmission error accuracies error it was clear that the amplitude has increased drastically and the same is visible in terms of the forces as shown in the above Figure 34 with red circle. There are certain spot of 500N force which is causing to damage the pinion flank. This was clearly visible in the actual product also.

1.13 The above-mentioned findings are consistent with the findings of the literature review. Friction has emerged as a significant characteristic for micropitting in the affected area once more. Lubricant film thickness is reduced in high-temperature zones, which is consistent with the results of the literature review.

1.14 Conclusion and Future scope

Experimental investigation was found in line with the analytical investigation. Micropitting occurred in the lower dedendum zone of the pinion. There was no change in microstructure before and after the micropitting and was showing no relation with micropitting. The vibration signals on account of micropitting were irrelevant, however if the experiments were continued to worst deterioration level, then vibration signals could have been of use for analysing it.

A promising next direction would be to conduct experimental analyses with varied speed and variable load conditions and compare the findings of this study work.

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